

MASS PRODUCTION COMPOSITES

Mr. A. Jardon
Directeur Technique du Groupe Renault
9-11 Avenue du 18 Juin 1940
92500 Rueil Malmaison
FRANCE

ABSTRACT

Materials have become during the last two decades a key factor of technological evolution. Many big achievements of our modern era have only been possible through the developments of new materials. And this is true for every field : aerospace, electronics, surgery medicine, automotive.

New materials have appeared and, among them : composite materials. Revolution has been a widely used word for qualifying their introduction in an industrial product.

However their use is usually **restricted to "High Performance/Small Volume"** industries. In this area, the constraints are very difficult :

- the weight must be minimal,
- the safety must be certain,
- the environment is very severe,

but the **cost of materials related to the complete cost of the total service is very low.**

In this paper we propose to look at the possibility of using Composite Materials in a Mass Production Industry where materials cost is a key factor : ie Automotive.

First we must consider the definition of a composite. Experience points out that this word "Composite" refers to different kinds of material depending on the people you speak to. An aerospace designer will think of high performance materials with continuous fibers, such as carbon or aramid. A car manufacturer will imagine polyesters with chopped glass fibers.

So in this paper we will keep as a definition : every reinforced plastic material is taken as a Composite.

1.2

The king of materials in automotive industry is metal. Steel and iron compose roughly 70 % of the weight of the car. However, composites materials are very exciting for the car designer :

- they are **versatile** and a wide range of properties can be reached, depending only on the material composition and on the process,

- they are **resistant to small impacts**,

- they **absorb energy very well**,

- they **do not rust**,

- they are **light**,

- and, as for the price, they **can be very competitive** if we consider their "function integration" capability (capability to make in one part what needs several parts in traditional solutions).

In a very competitive market, the winners will be those who can use every technological breakthrough in car design and manufacturing. Composites are a very big opportunity. For they can allow us to cut the cost and improve the quality in a way that traditional materials cannot. But to reach this goal, we have to be able to adapt the design of the whole car to the new material, and to learn to understand the complete behaviour of these materials under different stresses and constraints.

The first composites parts used in automotive industry were bumpers. The process used was SMC, that is compression of glass fibers preimpregnated with polyester. For ten years, thousands of bumpers a day were made with this technology. Now other opportunities appear, especially in body panels, suspension parts and frame parts.

We shall consider :

- body panels : a strong competition with steel for medium volume

In fact, composites have been used for years in small-volume car bodies. For this application indeed **technical advantages are added to economical gains**. Thus the ALPINE in France has been built, since its launching, in several polyester parts bonded together. And the more that is learnt about composites, the more cost effective their use becomes.

Now several medium-volume cars with composite panels are on the market. (up to 500 cars a day). We can note for instance two cars with the whole body in plastic materials, especially in composites :

- Fiero from GM Pontiac,
- Espace from RENAULT,

and two vehicles with some large parts in composites :

- BX from PSA,
- Express from RENAULT.

In all these cases, the material used is specific SMC. Some of these applications show that composites can combine high impact resistance with cosmetic properties.

Looking to the future we see on one hand several factors that can make the economic break-even point (between steel and plastic) move to larger series : **the cost-cutting through experience of designing** through composites and the **evolution of industrial constraints**, especially oven temperatures. On another hand, a car manufacturer's large series could be split into smaller series as a consequence of a need for flexibility due to a customer demand for model differentiation or a more frequent model change over.

However we must stress that the competition between steel and plastic will remain fierce and that even inside the family of plastic materials there will be a strong fight between thermoplastics and thermosets.

- suspension parts : design needs to be adapted to composites

Many companies are now interested in composite technologies for suspension. Several vehicles with composite leaf springs are today on the roads, for example :

- Sherpa from ROVER
- Vanette from NISSAN
- Corvette from GM
- Vans from GM and FORD
- Trafic from RENAULT.

For this application, the material is generally epoxy reinforced with glass. Several processes are applied or evaluated e.g. filament - winding, compression, pultrusion and pulforming, depending on the volume on the design and on the specific know-how of manufacturers.

The parts on the roads have shown the feasibility of the solution. But the application is still restricted to small-volume vans. The development in larger series needs a whole redesigning of the suspension in order to take future advantage of the specific properties of composites.

- frame parts : studies in an early stage

Recently several developments have been launched for frame parts such as chassis system, floor pan, front structure, front end, whole frame.

1.4

This research is in an early stage. The advantages of composites for these applications are their **"function integration capability"**. The main purpose is to reduce total cost by replacing a large number of parts by a much smaller number.

To reach this goal, it is necessary to control better the material, its consistency and its durability and to improve significantly the productivity of the processes.

In conclusion we can say that the knowledge of composites is brand new in the high-volume automotive industry. Designers are now learning how to use them. Many developments are possible, provided that we can reduce the costs and confirm the reliability.

This can be reached by learning to design with composites, controlling the behaviour of the material and developing adapted processes.

We have a challenge : to design, to engineer and to manufacture high-volume production vehicles with major components (body panels, suspension parts, frame) in composites.